

Introducing the Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) community

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ABSTRACT

In musculoskeletal (MSK) imaging research, scientists extract quantitative information from medical images to investigate chronic and debilitating diseases such as arthritis, osteoporosis, and neuromuscular diseases. The computational tools used to perform analyses are usually highly fragmented and often involve proprietary software, causing resource waste in re-implementations and ultimately slowing the advancement of the research field as a whole. The use of different code for evaluating similar processes also undermines scientific comparison and rigor. The ORMIR community aims to create and disseminate open, reproducible, well-tested, and well-documented software to analyze musculoskeletal images. Any interested scientists are welcome to join and contribute to the community.

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In musculoskeletal (MSK) imaging research, scientists extract quantitative information from medical images of joints, bones, and muscles to investigate chronic and debilitating diseases such as arthritis, osteoporosis, and muscular dystrophies (1–9). Computational tools used to perform analyses consist of workflows with a common structure: 1) acquisition of medical images using, e.g., computed tomography or magnetic resonance, either at the organ level (mm resolution) or tissue level (μm resolution in the order of); 2) segmentation of images to extract the MSK organs and tissues of interest—primarily bone, muscle, and cartilage; and 3) computation of metrics to quantify organ or tissue morphology, composition, and mechanical response. Variations across computational workflows are determined by implementation choices, including algorithms, computational parameters, and evaluation metrics.

Both within and across research laboratories, the underlying development of computational workflows is subject to several challenges. In research groups, locally developed code is usually fragmented, as it mainly consists of a combination of proprietary software and in-house algorithms. Proprietary software is often distributed with pre-set pipelines; thus, scientists can rarely verify parameters and implementations, creating difficulties in adapting the code to new images or anatomies. In addition, in-house software is often created as part of a specific project of limited duration. Consequently, code life is strictly linked to the employment of the code creators, restricting code reuse and expansion by newer lab members. It can also reduce the integrity of scientific results when studies cannot be directly compared due to dissimilar analysis approaches, limiting research reproducibility and falsification.

In the broader MSK imaging research community, software is usually not open source and, even when it is, it is often difficult to reuse because of lack of documentation (10), or it depends on proprietary languages and environments, such as MATLAB or Mathematica. Consequently, laboratories can rarely reuse existing code, unless they allocate resources to re-implementing algorithms from publications, which often lack implementation details (11,12). Further, absence of openly shared code at a community level limits compatibility with evolving technologies, expansion of code functionalities (13), comparison with new algorithms, and creation of validated standard procedures that can be trusted by the scientific community as a whole (14). Collaborations across laboratories would solve these challenges and potentially accelerate scientific discoveries in musculoskeletal research (15,16).

Several research communities in other disciplines have sought to tackle code fragmentation by creating open software distribution platforms. In genomic research, ‘Bioconductor’ is a software distribution that collects more than 2,000 packages written in the R programming language to analyze data ranging from single-cell sequencing to flow cytometry (17). In geoscience research, ‘Pangeo’ is a high-performance-computing environment with core packages for big data research, showcased by a rich Jupyter notebook gallery (18); the Pangeo community is followed by more than 5,000 researchers on Twitter and by more than 800 people on its blog medium.com/pangeo. In the brain imaging community, researchers coding in R can benefit from ‘Neuroconductor’, an open-source platform for rapid testing and dissemination of computational imaging software, currently hosting 86 packages (19).

Following the example of successful communities in other research fields, we established the Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) community, currently including more than 30 scientists from international academic institutions and industry. The proposal of code sharing, openness, and reproducibility as a solution to code fragmentation started circulating within the MSK imaging research community during satellite events¹ of the Quantitative Musculoskeletal Imaging (QMSKI) Workshop in 2019. A few months later, a group of nine researchers² took formal initiative and successfully applied for funds to hold a Jupyter Community Workshop. Originally planned for 2020, it was eventually held in 2022 due to the global pandemic (workshop report at (21)). Since the community was founded, the membership has increased in number, and members have started collaborating on computational workflows in four specific fields that address the musculoskeletal burden of arthritis, osteoporosis, and muscular dystrophies: quantification of bone and joint morphology from High-Resolution peripheral Quantitative Computed Tomography (HR-pQCT) images, image-based micro finite element modeling, standardization of data formats for magnetic resonance (MR) muscle imaging, and analysis of MR images of the knee (Table 1). Initial results were disseminated during concomitant events³ at the QMSKI 2022 workshop, and packages are currently under further development or maintenance.

The ORMIR community aims to continue creating and disseminating open, reproducible, well-tested, and well-documented software for analyzing musculoskeletal images. Future initiatives will include creating templates to homogenize code documentation and a certification system to standardize code. In the longer term, the community aims to share images and experimental data to create large datasets for cross-validation of algorithms and larger-scale computations. We will also seek to engage further with clinicians and clinical trial specialists to use these approaches to answer clinical questions relating to arthritis, osteoporosis, and neuromuscular diseases.

The ORMIR community regularly shares updates on releases, meetings, and events through a website (ormircommunity.github.io) and a Twitter account (@ORMIR_Community), and aims to convene

¹ “Hands-on Transparent QMSKI research: Open data, reproducible workflows, and interactive publications” organized by S. Bonaretti (20), and “Working group on standardization of quantitative metrics for 3D imaging” organized by A. Burghardt, P. Shneider, and S. Boyd

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³ “Introducing the Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) community” organized by S. Bonaretti, E. Schileo, and S. Manske (22), and “Are open and reproducible workflows necessary for CT in clinical trials and research” organized by S. Manske, A. Burghardt, and K. Stok

in-person around the time of the QMSKI workshop every two years. We invite any interested scientists to join our ORMIR community and contribute to accelerating and supporting advancement of quantitative MSK imaging research.

Python package name	Description	GitHub repository
<i>Packages developed with the support of the ORMIR community</i>		
Ciclope	Processing of micro computed tomography images to generate micro finite element models.	github.com/gianthk/ciclope
MuscleBIDS	Reading and writing a standardized data format for muscle MR imaging that is based on BIDS	github.com/muscle-bids/muscle-bids
ORMIR_XCT	Computing bone microarchitecture and joint space from HR-pQCT images	github.com/SpectraCollab/ORMIR_XCT
<i>Pre-existing packages created and maintained by members of the ORMIR community</i>		
pyKNEEr	Segmenting and analyzing femoral knee cartilage from MR images	github.com/sbonaretti/pyKNEEr
OAI analysis 2	Segmenting, registering, and analyzing femoral and tibial knee cartilage from the MR images of the whole OAI dataset	github.com/uncbiag/OAI_analysis_2
ITKIOScanco	An ITK module to read and write Scanco microCT .isq files	github.com/KitwareMedical/ITKIOScanco
Dafne	A segmentation tool for muscle MR images based on federated deep learning	github.com/dafne-imaging

Table 1. Python packages currently supported by the ORMIR community. Each GitHub repository contains the Python package and information on how to use it. Standardization of code style, documentation style, and file formats is under development. Abbreviations: MR: Magnetic Resonance; BIDS: Brain Imaging Data Structure (23); OAI: OsteoArthritis Initiative (24); HR-pQCT: High-Resolution peripheral Quantitative Computed Tomography.

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